

Deliverable 8.7

Responsible Research & Innovation Final report (RRI) Report 2020-2022

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0.4	16/1/22	Patricia Castillo. EURECAT	Internal review. Reviewed personal contact information of Ethics Board members as this deliverable is public.
1.0	27/01/22	Patricia Castillo. EURECAT	Final version for submission.

Executive Summary

This Deliverable reports the final Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) actions carried out during the final (3rd) year of the DIAMOND project and briefly summarises ethics issues over the life of the project.

The main ethics processes for DIAMOND and accompanying Guidelines were set up in year one (D8.2 and D8.4) and are as reported in the first annual report (D8.5).

Year 2 (2019-2020) activities mainly involved approval of remaining ethical decisions so that empirical research could be carried out (D8.6). This included adapting the research processes to take account of the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, particularly from around April 2020. This resulted in: a) the meetings of the ethics board being held online; b) additional applications to allow changes in data gathering due to the effects of the pandemic. Both of these changes resulted in amendments to original plans, however the research continued to operate effectively and the ethics revisions did not delay the overall project significantly.

In year 3 (2022-2022) there were no major ethical issues raised and some additional data collection instruments were given ethical approval.

Overall the ethical processes seem to have worked well for the project and partners.

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TERMINOLOGY AND ACRONYMS

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>GDPR</i>	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>RRI</i>	<i>Responsible Research & Innovation</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

I Introduction

This Deliverable reports the final Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) actions carried out during the final (3rd) year and briefly summarises ethics issues over the life of the project. The focus of this report is on the project's ethical processes and issues arising during ethical approvals and empirical research during year 3 (2020-2022) of the DIAMOND project. Actions related to the ethics processes and approvals, and ethical and research integrity issues that have arisen during the year 3 (including the 3 months project extension to January 2022) are set out.

The report builds on the RRI and legal reports for Year 1 (D8.5) and Year 2 (D8.6). The latter report includes a discussion of the major issues around the project adapting the research processes to take account of the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic, particularly from around April 2020. This resulted in: a) the meetings of the ethics board being held online for the remainder of the project; b) additional applications and amendments to applications to allow changes in data gathering due to the effects of the pandemic. Both of these seemed to have been amended and operate effectively and did not delay the project significantly.

Deliverable 8.2 describes the context for ethics considerations during the life of the project, including the ethical guidelines for social research across Europe are based on the joint development of specific rules and norms within different disciplines which have been created in line with research integrity expectations, the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR) Article 8 and current General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regulations. Of course all research in the DIAMOND project should follow relevant Horizon 2020, EU, national and discipline-based ethical and research integrity guidelines.

Given that Diamond conducts both primary and secondary data collection across all empirical WPs, it is necessary that a strong governance and ethics framework is embedded within the project. An ethical framework is required in order that both researchers and especially the participants taking part in the project can be assured that good practice has been met by the DIAMOND project, thus promoting confidence in the research and ensuring that the findings adhere to the appropriate ethical restrictions.

In general, ethical research is built on trust and integrity, including avoiding potential conflicts of interest or causing harm to participants or researchers and ensuring all data collected is handled properly. It helps ensure that participants involved in the research are provided with sufficient information to decide on whether or not to take part in the research, and that they explicitly and voluntarily give their informed consent to take part. All information gathered is considered anonymous and confidential unless explicit consent is given otherwise. Ethical research also avoids interviewing vulnerable people, unless essential to the research and there are careful safeguards in place to support this.

2 DIAMOND' ethics management structure

Project partners are aware of the ethical challenges facing an international and interdisciplinary project which not only collects primary data from participants across the partner countries but also involves analysing secondary data held by end user organisations. By utilising group work,

maintaining open and honest dialogue and mutual exchange between partners, we seek to work towards maintaining an unbiased attitude, developing well-defined ideological standpoints in order to preserve a sense of criticality throughout the project. An external (non-partner) member of the DIAMOND Advisory Board was invited to the board meetings as in all cases attempts were made to achieve a relatively independent view on ethics decisions. Where possible the ethics approval procedures of individual partners were used to gain approval, so as to have as independent a review of ethics applications as possible. Where this was not possible (generally where partners did not have a suitable internal ethics process and committee), applications would be made only to the DIAMOND ethics Board.

In year 1 STIR developed a range of ethics guidance documents to support the ethical collection of data for the DIAMOND project which can be found in D8.2 and D8.4.

2.1 Ethics Board Members

Name	Organisation	Secondary contact name
Francisco Santarremigia	AITEC	Gemma Molero
Ludovico Boratto	EURECAT	Lucia Recio
Piotr Załęcki	ZTM	Łukasz Filipczak
Elizabeth Young	WAVE	Robin Young
Rawad Choubassi	SYS	Andrea Gorrini
Paula Ciria Espinosa	FGC	J. Carles Terés Casals
Augustus Ababio-Donkor	ENU	Prof. Wafaa Saleh
Milos Milenkovic	FTTE	Filip Filipović
Chris Blache	GENRE ET VILLE	Pascale Lapalud
Alfonso Montella	RINA	Katia Vosilla
Ronald McQuaid	STIR	Yvonne Hail
External Reviewers	Rachel Palmen Cristina Marolda	

3 Ethics application decisions & Ethics board meetings minutes

In D8.6 (RRI Year 2 Report) we listed ethics applications still to be decided as:

Collection Technique	Use case
Structured Data	All (users and employees)
Focus Groups	All (users and employees)
Employee satisfactions Surveys	Use Case 4
User Satisfaction Surveys	Use case 1, 2 and 3
Observations	Use case 2 and 3

These applications were given full approval and data collection begun.

3.1 New Applications

3.1.1 Ethics Board Teleconference November 7th 2019 Observations for Use Cases

II and III

In Attendance at Meeting - Contributors to Report:

(Yvonne, Ronald) STIR, August (ENU), Lucia (EURECAT) Elena (AITEC), Milos (FTTE)

Main Applicant: SYS

Actions Completed:

Consider application for 'Observations for Use Cases II and III'

Decisions taken: *Approved with conditions.*

Ethics Board Recommendations: *Approved subject to conditions below:*

Information given:

- It states in the application a “maximum” of two people conducting observations, it was recommended that this should say “minimum” of two people in order to meet with risk assessment.
- That the application should have an additional statement added that states explicitly that each organisation will conduct risk assessments in the areas before the observations are conducted.
- Although not directly an ethical issue, it was highlighted that in appendix I there is comment regarding “paratransit”, no one on the ethics board was able to define the meaning of this term which is required to be translated into multiple languages for partners, therefore we ask that an explanation or definition is added to the observation protocol so that all partners can translate the concept accurately.

Next Steps:

The ethics board members then discussed how to plan the next application meeting as most of the ethics board are also applicants. It was agreed with Lucia (DIAMOND project manager) that STIR would draft an email to be sent to all ethics board members to explore suggestions on how best to take forward the application process for structured data collection.

Actions for Whom:

Yvonne and Ron STIR design draft email

Augustus ENU to send his suggestion in writing

Lucia EUT will then edit and send email to ethics board members

3.1.2 Ethics Board Teleconference December 11th 2019 Additional Applicants to DAD

In Attendance at Meeting - Contributors to Report:

Augustus (ENU) Milos (FTT) Ron and Yvonne (STIR)

Main Applicant: AITEC

Actions Completed:

The addition of the following partners to the ethics approval previously given for DAD survey. Additional applicants include: EURECAT, Genre et Ville (G&V), RINA, TUDublin, WAVE and ZTM.

Decisions taken: *Approved with conditions.*

Ethics Board Recommendations: Approved subject to conditions.

Information given:

Conditions: that EURECAT (Lucia) agree to and respond accordingly to the following points:

- The accompanying material for the DAD (surveys, participant information and consent etc.) have not changed significantly from the previous approved AITEC DAD application (approved 25/10/19).
- Each partner should ensure that the DAD complies with relevant legislation in their country. Some countries may have to remove some questions in order to meet their national legislation (e.g. France).
- For those DADs issued in the language of partners: each partner must ensure that any language translation are carried out to a high standard and checked by a native speaker of the relevant language.
- It is noted that FGC and VEBLIB are not part of this application and that they will not be collecting or analysing the data (so Q B1d and C1b exclude 'FGC', despite the typo stating that they would).
- It is noted that in C9 on dissemination, 'reports' includes public DIAMOND project reports to the European Commission.

Next Steps:

Actions on Whom:

That EURECAT agree to and respond accordingly to the following points.

3.1.3 Ethics Board Teleconference December 18th 2019 Structured Data Application and Observations for Use Case III

In Attendance at Meeting:

Augustus (ENU – left during meeting but left when the two applications were being discussed as they involved ENU) Elizabeth (WAVE), Lucia (EURECAT), Mary (TUDublin) and Ron and Yvonne (STIR)

Main Applicant: SYS

Actions Completed:

Structured Data Application and Observations for Use Case III

Approved with conditions. Chair's action - The chair (Ron) was delegated to approve the minor amendments on behalf of the Ethics Board.

Decisions taken: **Approved with conditions.**

Structure data application by SYS; ENU and VELIB Approved.

Observations Use Case III by SYS; ENU and VELIB Approved subject to conditions.

Information given:

- Conditions: Annex I of the application should be changed to reflect:
- 'Participant Observation' should be changed to 'Non-participant observation' (or a note included stating that Participants in the observation would not engage or interact directly with the researchers).
- Focus groups are taking place after the observations not before.
- There should be no interviews carried out as part of the observations. If interviews are to be carried out then a further ethics application is required with the standard information (e.g. Consent forms, questionnaire etc.).
- Clarify or delete: "Activities that are important to understanding use case III should be focussed on, while extraneous and unimportant activities should not receive much attention in the field notes".
- Clarify what data in the 'Use-case III Observation check list' is gathered by observation and what from secondary sources (e.g. 'Is it a low-income or minority neighbourhood?'; 'Does the station have female membership?').
- Q 5.3 Not all minorities can be observed visually, so this question should be deleted.

Next Steps:

In addition the Ethics Board noted a number of research issues which, while not raising major ethical issues, should be considered by the researchers: There should be a protocol so that all researchers score similar stations in the same way (Q 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.7, 2.10, 4.1 – e.g. 'Does the station have adequate lighting?').

Q 1.3 and 1.13 are duplicates.

Actions on Whom:

ENU to make the required revisions and then pass the revised document to the ethics chair (Ron McQuaid).

3.1.4 Ethics Board Teleconference February 12th 2020 UESI questionnaires

In Attendance at Meeting - Contributors to Report:

Lucía (Eurecat), Rachel (External Advisor) and Milos (FTTE)

Main Applicant: All partners

Actions Completed:

UESI questionnaires All partners together reviewed application forms, discussed potential issues and made a conclusion. The details are provided below:

Section A: No applicant issues identified.

Section B: No ethical issues identified. Some clarifications are needed.

Section C: No ethical issues identified.

Decisions taken: Approved.

Members of the DIAMOND ethics board agreed that application could be passed without conditions. Pending to receive approval from ZTM (out of office this week), who have revised application but not yet given their approval.

Information given:

Ask to clarify the sample size which is confusing in sections B and C.

NO DIAMOND risk assessment is included in the application. This should be carried out.

In case of subcontracting interviewers for conducting questionnaires in stations, organizations need to guarantee that external companies follow ethical rules.

Next Steps: -

Actions on whom: - ZTM approval received

3.1.5 Ethics Board Teleconference 16th July 2020 UESI Focus Groups and Telephone/Online Interviews

In Attendance at Meeting - Contributors to Report:

Carlos (FGC), Lukasz (ZTM), Piotr (ZTM), Lucia (EURECAT) – not-available online due to health issues, however, she has reviewed the documents without any objection on present form. Milos (FTTE).

Main Applicant: TUDublin

Actions Completed:

The documents reviewed are as follows:

1. Ethical approval form: UESI Focus Groups and Telephone/Online Interviews – UC I, III, IV
2. COVID19 Questions
3. DIAMOND Project Participant Information Sheet
4. Process Document for qualitative data collection for UC I and UC4.
5. Telephone/Online interview UC4
6. Online focus group for UC I
7. HR Interviews for UC4

Decisions taken: Approved.

All the members of the DIAMOND ethics board (and Lucia (EURECAT)) agreed that the application forms do not contain potential issues from an ethical point of view.

3.1.6 Ethics Board 5th October 2020 Email.

Amendment to the application form for data collection through the UESI questionnaire already approved

Actions Completed:

For use case III it is foreseen that of a multi-store gift vouchers (10€ face value) may be used to encourage participants response levels.

Addition of the following sentence “For use case III it is foreseen that of a multi-store gift vouchers (10€ face value) may be used to help participants buy rain cape, hi-vis jacket etc. (or something connected with riding a bike) to gain a better chance of achieving a higher response rate in a relative short time”.

Decisions taken: by email

Prof. R McQuaid Ethics Chair Fri 02/10/2020 14:44

I am happy to take chair’s action and approve it. My reasons are:

It should not harm the participants in any way and should not affect their specific answers to questions or otherwise bias the results. It should, however, increase the response rate and the range of respondents, especially from those who may be influenced by the token award including perhaps those on lower incomes etc. and so improve the representativeness of the findings among under- represented groups.

I think the amendment to the original application of adding the possibility a token (10 euro) incentive is minor in these circumstances. Hence it is acceptable to use chair's action rather than reconvene the entire committee to agree it.

- However, before finalising the decision can you please send this email to those on the committee (not the applicants) so they can object to this approval if they wish (in which case we will happily convene a full committee meeting to discuss it). Perhaps give them until the middle of next week to reply if they want.

Project Coordinator Lucia Recio Naranjo Mon 05/10/2020 09:21

After discussion with Ronald McQuaid, DIAMOND's Ethic Board and as there are no likely negative impacts (to participants or the quality of results etc.) from offering the small incentive to participate. We agreed the following:

Due to it should not harm the participants in any way and should not affect their specific answers to questions or otherwise bias the results. It should, however, increase the response rate and the range of respondents, especially from those who may be influenced by the token award including perhaps those on lower incomes etc. and so improve the representativeness of the findings among under- represented groups.

I think the amendment to the original application of adding the possibility a token (10 euro) incentive is minor in these circumstances. Hence it is acceptable to use chair's action rather than reconvene the entire committee to agree it.

However, before finalising the decision we'll be happy to receive your comments in case you want to object this approval (in which case we will happily convene a full committee meeting to discuss it). Please, let us know your thoughts before Wednesday EOB.

Best Regards, Lucía

Decision taken: [Approved](#).

There have been no major ethical issues found during the approval meetings.

All ethics applications for data collection and any amendments in relation to the impact of COVID-19 have now been completed.

3.1.7 Ethics Board Teleconference 14th January 2022

In Attendance at Meeting – Rawad (SYS), Andrea (SYS), Lukasz (ZTM), Mary, Chiara (DUT), Milos (FTTE), Elizabeth (WAVE), Chris (Genre et Ville)

Main Applicant: AITEC (+Eurecat and IBV)

Actions Completed:

The documents reviewed are as follows:

1. Ethical approval form: feedback from relevant stakeholders about the DIAMOND's guideline "Autonomous Vehicles through gender perspective glasses"
2. DIAMOND Project Participant Information Sheet
3. Clarification of online participant information and consent (Ricard Barberà-Guillem, IBV)

Decisions taken: [Approved with one condition.](#)

All the members of the DIAMOND ethics board (and Lucia (EURECAT)) agreed to approve the application, with one condition. The information at the start of the survey should briefly state how, and for how long, the data is stored (e.g. safely stored for a maximum of 5 years) and a contact name and email should be provided (e.g. the data manager or another contact, but not the researcher issuing the survey) in case the participant has any issues with the survey.

4 Audit of Each Partner

AITEC

On November 2019, the ethics application for the DAD was approved after all of the conditions were addressed.

On 12th of March 2021, the DIAMOND Ethics Board has agreed to approve the application received on 10 March by AITEC, WAVE, Genre et Ville, TUD and Eurecat, led by Francisco Santarremigia for the survey to collect Fairness Measures linked to the most relevant Fairness Measures for Women.

On 10th of June 2021, the ethics application for the workshop to validate Fairness Measures was approved after all the conditions were considered.

ENU

UESI data collection for Use Case III approved.

EURECAT

Data Collection through Focus groups, social media and DAD survey all approved.

FGC

Sociodemographic questions were reviewed by FGC ethics committee and some were identified as non compliant with FGC ethics.

FTTE

No ethical issues or considerations.

G&V

Observation, Focus Group and Individual Interviews all approved.

IBV

All ethics approval for data collection approved by Comité de ética en investigación de la Universitat Politecnica de Valencia. 31/10/2019.

RINA

No reply from partners.

STIR

Stirling chaired the ethics meetings and edited the relevant reports. They also provided individual advice to various partners on potential issues.

SYS

Structure Proprietary Data (Use Case I and Use Case III) all approved.

TUDublin

Application (16 July 2020) approved.

WAVE

No ethical issues or concerns.

ZTM

Data collection focus groups, structured data, observations, UESI questionnaires, social media data and DAD survey all ethics approval granted.

5 Ethical Issues Arising in Project

All partners co-operated well in ensuring that suitable ethical processes were set up and followed throughout the life of the project.

Most research in the project was in the form of surveys (mainly online), interviews and focus groups. The various Deliverables on Guidance and principles for research and Data Management resulted in early agreement between partners on ethical research and clear expectations for behaviour, together with agreed ethical processes, that were followed throughout the project. *It was useful that this general agreement and clarity of expectations occurred early in the project.*

Where possible *external ethical approval* was used (e.g. from a partner's own organisation's ethical committee) and this was beneficial in getting external views on the relevant ethical issues. Also

chair's action was only considered where timing was a major issue and the proposals were not substantially different from previously approved applications.

Overall the *time for ethics applications and processes* was reasonable as generally applications were done as early as possible before the empirical research was to be carried out and where this was not possible (e.g. due to changes due to COVID-19) all partners contributed quickly and effectively to the decision-making process (see Minutes above).

Overall COVID-19 and the roll out of social restrictions across Europe impacted on the project's *data collection process, especially in terms of conducting focus groups and face to face interviews, particularly from around April 2020 when data gathering was increasing. In the majority of cases all data collection was moved to online platforms which required a review of ethics applications and approvals. This was completed and, where appropriate, approval given.*

Also due to COVID-19 the application process was carried out online (via email submissions) and all meetings of the ethics Panel after early 2020 were carried out online.

Ethics partners (WP8 STIR) provided general advice and regular reminders to partners to be cognisant of ethics principles in all data collection, storage and analysis processes.

In Year 2 amendments were made to the ethics application for Use Case III to *add an incentive of a 10 Euro voucher to encourage people to take part in the process. The voucher was designed to be used to help purchase biking equipment such as water proof clothes or high visibility jackets.*

Due to local decisions and requirements, not all partners used the same *demographic question sheet* developed by the project (e.g., in France certain demographic data could not be collected due to national legislation).

A *survey to partners* was distributed in August 2021 to assess *partners' perceptions of the ethical standards, practices and procedures* provided valuable feedback regarding ethics upon the culmination of this project.

Results indicated:

Firstly, one third of the partners who provided feedback (3/9) reported facing specific ethical issues in year 3. These related to the workshops to collect and validate the Fairness Measures/Characteristics (AITEC), the development of the public toolbox (FGC) and the need to modify data collection from in person to online focus groups and interviews (TUDublin). Partners reported unanimously that these *ethical issues were resolved satisfactorily* with input and support from the ethics board/committee and the ethics approval process and by modifying the original application to account for the change in conditions (the impact of the Covid 19 pandemic).

Secondly, only 2 partners reported facing *significant ethical issues in carrying out research* throughout the project, both in terms of data collection (AITEC, FGC) and in both instances these issues were resolved satisfactorily.

Finally, only one partner suggested they had faced *significant ethical issues in the ethics approval process throughout the project*. These issues were around data collection campaigns for one Work Package (AITEC), however the ethics approval process and ethics board provided appropriate recommendations allowing the issues to be resolved satisfactorily.

As evidenced above, in general the ethics process developed for the DIAMOND project has worked well. There was a bigger work load than initially expected due to changes in ethics obligations after the application for the project was made, and due to COVID-19 and changes made to research instruments.

6 Conclusions and Lessons Learned

The ethics process helped ensure integrity in the research carried out in the project. It also sought to identify any ethical issues and remove them before any empirical research was carried out (although this did not needed in any significant way). The main ethics processes for DIAMOND and accompanying Guidelines were completed in year 1 (D8.2 and D8.4) and updated for Year 2 (D8.6). Year 3's activities mainly involved approval of some new ethical applications (due to changes to research following COVID-19) and remaining ethical decisions so that empirical research could be carried out. In addition ongoing general discussions on ethical issues were continued and specific advice where needed, was provided.

The impacts of Covid-19 greatly affected the project particularly from around April 2020. This resulted in: a) the meetings of the ethics board being held online; b) additional applications to allow changes in data gathering methods due to the effects of the pandemic. Both of these seemed to have been amended and operate effectively and did not significantly delay the project carrying out the new fieldwork.

The results of the ethics survey (distributed in August 2021) assessing partners perceptions of the ethical standards, practices and procedures highlights some 'lessons learned' and importantly evidence of 'good practice' throughout the course of the DIAMOND project.

With regard 'lessons learned' it was reported that better planning by partners regarding the ethical implications of data collection would avoid the need for recurring applications to the ethics committee, and that revision of issues such as terminology and research details and understanding that appropriate and acceptable questioning varies from location to location, is fundamental to uphold the ethics of the study.

With regard 'good practice' feedback from respondents was very positive. It was considered that ethical issues were managed well and resolved and that the ethics process was well structured and robustly managed. The continuity in the ethics board members was also considered good practice, alongside the ability of the members to identify ethical issues and ensure adherence to ethical standards. It was also considered valuable to have an independent committee providing peer-to-peer feedback regarding data collection. Finally, the flexibility employed by the ethics committee with regard to membership of the Ethics Board meant that conflicts of interest were avoided at all times, with ethics submissions being evaluated by those external to that specific submission.

